

Assessment of halloysite nanotubes as vehicles of isoniazid

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Abstract

Equilibrium and thermodynamic aspects of the adsorption of isoniazid (INH) onto halloysite nanotubes (HLNTs) and characteristics of the resultant drug/nanocarrier systems are investigated. Equilibrium studies were performed in aqueous medium at different times, temperatures and drug concentrations. The overall adsorption process was explained as the result of two simple processes: adsorption on the activated sites of HLNTs and precipitation of INH on HLNTs surface. Formation of the INH-loaded HLNTs was spontaneous, endothermic and endoentropic, increasing the thermodynamic stability of the system ($\Delta H = 70.40$ kJ/mol; $\Delta S = 0.2519$ kJ/molK). Solid state characterization corroborated the effective interaction between the components that was also described by modeling at molecular level by quantum mechanics calculations along with empirical interatomic potentials. Transmission electron microphotographs confirmed the double allocation and homogeneous distribution of INH in the nanohybrids. FTIR spectra revealed the interaction via hydrogen bonds between the inner hydroxyl groups of HLNTs and N in INH molecules. Loading of INH in the nanohybrids was approximately 20% w/w. Effective loading of INH and activation energies of the interactions enable to propose the designed nanohybrids in the development of modified drug delivery systems.

Keywords: Isoniazid, Halloysite, Adsorption, Thermodynamics, Molecular modeling, Nanohybrids

1. Introduction

Tuberculosis (TB) ranks as the second leading cause of death worldwide from an infectious disease, particularly in development countries, only surpassed by the human immunodeficiency virus [1]. It is estimated that one third of the world's population is infected with *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, with over 10 million new patients in 2015 and almost half a million of new cases of multidrug-resistant TB [1]. High morbidity and mortality rates make also the development of effective TB treatments an important global health priority [2]. The currently recommended treatment for new cases of TB consists on a six-month regimen of four first-line drugs (isoniazid, rifampicin, ethambutol and pyrazinamide), with a relatively low cost of about US\$ 40 per person

[1]. However, two factors determine a poor adherence to the therapy, especially in developed nations: its long-term duration and polymedication [3]. As a result of the low patient compliance, multidrug-resistant TB increases globally, requiring longer and more expensive treatments [1]. The design and development of new modified drug delivery systems arises as a good strategy to reduce the frequency of drug administration, increasing compliance and reducing resistant TB incidence [2,4]. A wide range of nanoparticulated systems have been proposed to modify drug delivery [5-12], even if most of them are based on expensive materials and/or technologies. The use of clay minerals as carriers for these systems appears as a low cost and biocompatible alternative [13-15]. In particular, halloysite is a multilayer nanotubular material resulting from the wrapping of 1:1 layers of kaolinite [16-18]. Halloysite nanotubes (HLNTs) have been proposed as a natural vehicle for encapsulation and modified release of several drugs [19-24]. With these premises, the aim of this work was to design INH/HLNTs hybrids useful in modified drug delivery treatment of TB. Equilibrium and thermodynamics aspects of the adsorption process between INH and HLNTs were fully investigated and the hybrid systems were then characterized by solid state techniques in order to determine the nature and degree of the interactions between the clay surfaces and the drug molecules. Complementary molecular modeling of the INH/HLNTs adsorption process was carried out in terms of quantum mechanics calculations along with empirical interatomic potentials devoted to determine the most important interaction sites and to investigate mechanisms involved in the adsorption process.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

INH (Fig. 1) and HLNTs were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Spain).

Fig. 1. INH structure

2.2. Adsorption studies

Adsorption experiments were carried out via intercalation solution technique to obtain equilibrium isotherms at different times and temperatures. 0.1 g of HLNTs were added to 20 ml of INH aqueous solutions with initial concentration (C_0) ranging from 0.05 to 0.5 M, in 25 ml PyrexTM glass flasks and stirred (150 rpm) in a thermostated bath for different times (24h, 48h, one week and two weeks) at 30 ± 0.1 °C. The resulting suspensions were then centrifuged and the equilibrium concentration (C_e) of the drug in the supernatant was determined by UV spectroscopy (UV-vis spectrophotometer Lambda 25, Perkin Elmer, S) at 262 nm. The difference between the initial and equilibrium drug concentration was assumed to be due to drug adsorption onto HLNTs and the amount of INH retained per gram of clay was calculated. One week experiments were also done at different temperatures ($35, 40 \pm 0.1$ °C), once confirmed that this time was long enough to ensure that equilibrium was reached between INH adsorbed

and INH in solution. Mathematical treatment of the data was performed [25], using the software packaging TableCurve 2D® (Systat Software Inc., UK) and the relevant adsorption parameters were obtained including monolayer adsorption capacity and equilibrium rate constants.

2.3. Solid state characterization

Hybrid systems prepared at 30 °C and initial concentration ($C_0 = 0,25$ mol/L) to achieve the monolayer adsorption capacity of HLNTs were characterized to determine the effective drug loading, the chemical groups involved in the adsorption process, as well as the presence and distribution of the drug in the internal lumen and/or external surface of HLNTs.

2.3.1. X-ray powder diffraction

X-Ray powder diffraction (XRPD) was done by using a Philips® X-Pert diffractometer with Cu K α radiation, 40 kV, 40 mA, 3–70° 2θ exploration range, 6° 2θ min⁻¹ scanning speed, 1×10^3 sensitivity and 2 s time constant. The diffraction data were analysed using the XPOWDER® software [26]. The experiments were run in triplicate (experimental error $\pm 5\%$).

2.3.2. Electron microscopy studies

Samples were stained by drop deposition with uranyl acetate 2% (w/v) aqueous solution to achieve selective fixation of uranyl to the amino groups of the drug molecules [27]. Briefly, dehydrated samples were embedded for 2 h in a mixture of ethanol and epoxy resin for microscopy (EMbed 812, EMS Ltd., UK) and then included for 24 h in pure resin. Subsequently, polymerization was performed by heating the samples at 37 °C for 24 h and then at 70 °C for 24 h. The polymerized blocks, cut into ultrathin slices (900 Å thickness) and placed on 300-mesh TEM copper grids (Neyco, France) were stained by deposition of uranyl acetate 2% (w/v) aqueous solution. The excess of the staining agent was absorbed onto filter paper and then grids were covered with a carbon film. The uranyl-stained samples were examined using a FEI Titan G2 60-300 ultra-high resolution transmission electron microscope (UHRTEM), coupled with analytical electron microscopy performed with a SUPER-X silicon-drift windowless energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) detector. The AEM spectra were collected in STEM (Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy) mode using a HAADF (High Angle Annular Dark Field) detector. X-ray chemical element maps were also collected.

2.3.3. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectra were recorded on a FTIR spectrophotometer (JASCO 6200, with software SPECTRA MANAGER v2 and with an attenuated total reflectance (ATR) accessory). Measurements were carried out from 400 to 4000 cm⁻¹ at 0.25 cm⁻¹ resolution.

2.3.4. Thermal analysis

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) were carried out by using a METTLER TOLEDO mod. TGA/DSC1 with FRS5 sensor and a microbalance (precision 0.1 µg) (Mettler-Toledo GMBH). Samples were heated in air atmosphere at 10 °C /min. Analyses were done in triplicate.

2.4. Molecular modeling methodology and models

The INH molecule was taken from the crystallographic data of crystal form [28]. Our solid models were generated from the atomic coordinates of a slide of an HLNT from previous works [29] with the stoichiometry $\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5(\text{OH})_4$. Periodic boundary conditions were applied to create a periodical crystal structure with the a and b cell parameters crossing the tube forming a cylinder section and the c cell parameter along the HLNT length. We established $a = 50 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 50 \text{ \AA}$ large enough values for crystal lattice parameters in order to avoid interactions between vicinal tubes. However, the c cell parameter should be optimized point by point in order to connect the original slide to the next one forming a bridging O-Si distance similar of the others O-Si bonds. Then, this optimization yielded a value of $c = 9.05 \text{ \AA}$ with the $d(\text{O-Si}) = 1.67 \text{ \AA}$. Hence, our unit cell of HLNT was a cylinder with an internal diameter of 27 \AA formed with an external layer of Si oxide tetrahedra joined to an internal layer of aluminium hydroxide octahedral. The structure is neutral and the multilayer cylindrical structure was possible enlarging the AlOAl and OSiO angles to form the cylinder curvature. Hence, our unit cell of HLNT has the formula $\text{Al}_{76}\text{Si}_{76}\text{O}_{190}(\text{OH})_{152}$ with 646 atoms. In some cases to avoid intermolecular interactions between adsorbates of vicinal cells a $1 \times 1 \times 2$ supercell was generated of HLNT, $\text{Al}_{152}\text{Si}_{152}\text{O}_{380}(\text{OH})_{304}$, with 1292 atoms. In natural HLNTs the internal diameter is around 15-50 nm, nevertheless our models can represent a good scenario to reproduce the interactions at molecular level of the adsorption process.

The optimization of HLNT structure was performed with quantum mechanical calculations by using Density Functional Theory (DFT) with CASTEP code, within the generalized gradient approximation (GGA), the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) correlation exchange functional and the cut off energy of 300eV [30]. The adsorbate was placed over the internal surface of the nanotube with the heterocycle ring in a parallel disposition with respect to surface at an average distance of 3 \AA to the hydroxyl groups of the mineral surface. The adsorbed complexes were optimized maintaining the mineral structure fixed by using empirical interatomic potentials with the Compass force field that has provided good results in previous studies [30-32]. For non-bonding interactions, the coulomb and van de Waals interactions were calculated by the Ewald method with a cut-off of 12 \AA .

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Equilibrium studies

The experimental equilibrium isotherms obtained at different adsorption times as n^s (moles of solute retained per gram of adsorbent) vs C_e are plotted in Fig. 2. The curves showed initial convex shapes, typical of L-class of Giles classification [33]. The behaviour at higher concentrations allowed further classifying the curves as L3 class, characterized by an inflection point from a plateau phase to concave profiles. This behaviour suggested possible precipitation of drug molecules on HLNTs surface. In comparison with short times (one day and two days), an enhanced delineation of the plateau phase was observed after one week, with no further improvement in equilibrium profiles at longer times. Consequently, one week was chosen as the optimal time to suitably define the adsorption curves.

Data obtained from one-week experiments were fitted to the following continuous function:

$$n^s = n_1^s + n_2^s = \sum_{i=1}^{i=2} \frac{K_i \cdot n_m^s \cdot C}{K_i \cdot C + 1} + k_f C^m \quad (1)$$

where n^s = mol of sorbate adsorbed per gram of sorbent, n_m^s = monolayer retention capacity, C = equilibrium concentration, k_i = kinetic equilibrium constant, k_f = kinetic precipitation constant and m = constant.

Equation (1) suggests that the overall adsorption was the sum of two single processes: adsorption at the active surface sites of the sorbent (n_1^s) followed by precipitation of drug molecules (n_2^s) over the adsorbed monolayer [25].

Fig. 2. Equilibrium isotherms of INH onto HLNTs at different times (mean values \pm s.d.; $n = 3$).

The theoretical overall adsorption curves and contribution of single adsorption processes (n_1^s , n_2^s) resulting from data fitting are shown in Fig. 3.

At the studied temperatures, the initial contribution at lower drug concentrations was the n_1^s process, whereas precipitation process (n_2^s) was significant only once the plateau phase was reached (C_e approximately 0.15M), becoming predominant at higher concentrations. The calculated parameters of Eq. (1) are shown in Table 1.

The monolayer adsorption capacity (n_m^s) increased with decreasing temperature, apparently suggesting that adsorption took place as an exothermic process. However, the trending of k_i values was compatible with an endothermic process. To elucidate the energetic behaviour of the system, k_i values were used to derive the thermodynamic activation functions by means of the following Eq. (2) [34]:

$$\ln \frac{k_i}{T} = \ln \frac{R}{Nh} + \frac{\Delta S^\circ}{R} - \frac{\Delta H^\circ}{R} \times \frac{1}{T} \quad (2)$$

where k_i = kinetic equilibrium constant, R = gas constant, N = Avogadro's number, h = Planck's constant, T = temperature (K).

The calculated values are given in Table 1, which also includes ΔG (activation energy) values (calculated from the expression $\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S$). The ΔH and ΔS values indicated that the adsorption of INH onto HLNTs was an endothermic and endoentropic process. The endothermic

behaviour reflects that loss of solvation molecules (INH) is required for the incorporation of the adsorbable solute in the adsorbed phase. Otherwise, the positive ΔS value is due to the lower mobility of the adsorbed INH molecules, increasing the order of the system. Finally, the negative ΔG values revealed that at the studied conditions the adsorption process is thermodynamically spontaneous.

Fig. 3. Average experimental and theoretical equilibrium isotherms of INH onto HLNTs obtained at one week and three different temperatures (30°C, 35°C and 40°C).

Table 1
Fitting parameters of Eqs. (1) and (2). for the adsorption of INH onto HLNTs at different temperatures and ΔG (activation energy) for the INH/HLNTs interaction.

T (°C)	Eq. (1)				Eq. (2)		
	n_m^s (mol/g)	k_i	k_f	M	ΔH° (kJ/mol)	ΔS° (kJ/molK)	ΔG (kJ/mol)
30	0.0025 ± 0.0002	11.271 ± 0.4865	0.508 ± 0.0245	5.116 ± 0.2147	70.40 ± 1.244	0.2519 ± 0.00127	-5.9257 ± 0.00021
35	0.0023 ± 0.0001	15.001 ± 0.3587	0.155 ± 0.0155	3.732 ± 0.1234			-7.1852 ± 0.00015
40	0.0021 ± 0.0001	27.575 ± 0.2111	0.128 ± 0.0872	3.513 ± 0.6547			-8.4447 ± 0.00071

3.2. Solid state characterisation

3.2.1. XRPD

The powder X-ray diffraction patterns of the hybrid systems (INH-loaded HLNTs) and their individual components are given in Fig. 4. INH showed a crystalline pattern, with main reflections at around 10° , 14° , 16° and 20° 2θ , characteristic of the drug crystals [35], whereas HLNTs showed the typical pattern of natural dehydrated halloysite, with a diffraction peak at 12.25° 2θ , corresponding to a d_{001} -spacing of 7.24 \AA [36]. The dehydrated state was further confirmed by the presence of the 002 basal reflection at 24.55° 2θ [37]. INH-loaded HLNTs pattern was similar to that of HLNTs, including weak reflections coherent with the presence of crystalline INH over the adsorbed drug monolayer. This finding is in line with the beginning of the precipitation process at the plateau phase, as discussed previously (Fig. 3).

Fig. 4. XRPD patterns of INH-loaded HLNTs and their pure components (INH and HLNTs).

3.2.2. HREM/XEDS

Ultra-high resolution transmission electron microphotographs of the uranyl stained samples (Fig. 5) revealed the characteristic hollow tubular structure of the clay mineral both in native HLNTs (Fig. 5A1) and the hybrid system (Fig. 5B1). XEDS spectra of selected areas are also included in both cases, showing peaks of the nanotube components (O, Al and Si) and a weak Cu peak from the grids used to support the samples. The presence of uranium peaks in the nanohybrid XEDS (Fig. 5B1) allows us to confirm the effective loading of the drug. Uranyl was detected both in the interior (1) and edge (2) of halloysite tubules, which indicates the double allocation of INH molecules. X-ray maps of Si (Fig. 5A2 and B2), Al (Fig. 5A3 and B3) and U (Fig. 5A4 and B4) evidenced the elemental composition of the nanotubes as well as the homogeneous distribution of INH in the hybrid systems.

Fig. 5. UHRTEM microphotographs, XEDS analysis and elemental X-Ray maps of HLNTs (left) and INH-loaded HLNTs (right).

3.2.3. FTIR

FTIR spectra of the loaded nanotubes were compared to those of individual components to describe the probable interaction mechanisms (Fig. 6). INH showed a band at 3303 cm^{-1} , due to N-H stretching vibrations. Bands at 1552 cm^{-1} and 1410 cm^{-1} corresponded to the ring C=N stretching (amide II) and the ring C=C symmetric stretching, respectively. Ring asymmetric bending were noticed twice by both bands at 1193 cm^{-1} stating for a ring C-C-H asymmetric bending and a ring C-C-C asymmetric bending with band at 745 cm^{-1} . The band observed at 886 cm^{-1} confirmed a C-N-C ring bending. The band at 1661 cm^{-1} was due to carbonyl of amide group stretching vibrations, while the one at 1631 cm^{-1} owed to the NH_2 deformation. Another band at 1331 cm^{-1} was attributed to C-N stretching vibrations, while a band at 1556 cm^{-1} was assigned to N-H bending vibrations [35,38,39].

The infrared spectrum of HLNTs showed bands at 3692 cm^{-1} and 3621 cm^{-1} , assigned to two Al_2OH -stretching bands. Band at 3670 cm^{-1} , detected under a noise level of 0.1, was attributed to the O-H stretching of inner-surface hydroxyl groups, while the one at 3545 cm^{-1} was referred to the out-of-phase vibration of the inner surface hydroxyls. The band at 1647 cm^{-1} revealed bending vibrations of the physically adsorbed water. The band at 1098 cm^{-1} was assigned to apical Si-O. Perpendicular stretching Si-O-Si vibrations were registered at 679 cm^{-1} . The peaks at 749 cm^{-1} and 796 cm^{-1} were assigned to OH translation vibration of halloysite OH units [40-42]. The INH-loaded HLNTs showed the above mentioned HLNTs Al_2OH -stretching bands at 3693 cm^{-1} and 3622 cm^{-1} , as well as those corresponding to the perpendicular Si-O-Si stretching vibrations (673 cm^{-1}), OH translation vibration of halloysite units (747 cm^{-1} and 793 cm^{-1}) and bending vibrations of the physically adsorbed water (1654 cm^{-1}). The band attributed to INH ring C-C-H asymmetric bending (1119 cm^{-1}), appeared in the INH- loaded HLNTs spectra at 1193 cm^{-1} . NH_2 deformation band which in INH spectra appeared at 1631 cm^{-1} , was also present in the spectra of the INH-loaded HLNTs but at a wavelength of 1654 cm^{-1} . However, the band at 3545 cm^{-1} , caused by the out of phase vibration of the inner surface hydroxyl in HLNTs was not observed in the spectrum of the INH-loaded HLNTs. Moreover, the little band noticeable at 3670 cm^{-1} in HLNTs spectrum, attributed to the O-H stretching of inner-surface hydroxyl groups, also disappeared in the INH-loaded HLNTs spectrum. These changes are clearly related with the interaction via hydrogen bonds between the inner hydroxyl groups of HLNTs and N in INH molecules.

3.2.4. Thermal analysis

DSC curve of INH showed an endothermic peak at $175\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, corresponding to the melting of the drug, followed by an exothermic process beginning at $250\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, due to decomposition (Fig. 7). DSC curves of HLNTs and INH-loaded HLNTs did not show any significant enthalpy changes at the studied temperature interval and conditions. TGA analysis allowed a more detailed comprehension of the thermal behaviour of the samples (Fig. 7). TGA curve of INH showed a complete loss of mass in the interval $150\text{ }^\circ\text{C} - 350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, corresponding to the decomposition of the drug, and associated to the exothermic process observed in the DSC curve (Fig. 7). HLNTs exhibited two major mass losses at $100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ approximately, attributed to dehydration of the physically adsorbed water [43] and a second loss in the interval $400\text{ }^\circ\text{C} - 600\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, ascribed to dehydroxylation of the structural aluminol groups (AIOH) [44]. HLNTs is an extremely thermostable material, with a solid residue of $85.2 \pm 0.09\%$ w/w% of the initial mass at $1000\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Fig. 6. FTIR spectra of INH-loaded HLNTs and their pure components (INH and HLNTs).

Fig. 7. DSC and TGA curves of INH-loaded HLNTs and their pure components (INH and HLNTs).

TGA curve of INH-loaded HLNTs showed the decomposition of the drug as well as the dehydroxylation of the clay. Weight loss ascribed to INH decomposition was calculated according to the rule of mixtures for the residual masses at 1000 °C and taking into account the water content (weight loss between 25 and 150 °C) [45]. The calculated value ($18.9 \pm 0.12\%$ w/w) was in line with the theoretical amount of INH retained by the nanotubes calculated from the n_m^s at 30°C (25.5% w/w).

3.3. Molecular modeling

The adsorption of the INH molecule in the space of HLNTs was studied to determine the most important interaction sites with the mineral. This adsorption was simulated in both of two halloysite models and one INH molecule was placed over the internal surface of HLNTs. Dry conditions without presence of water molecules were used to avoid additional interactions that can hide the actual adsorbate-surface interactions. In the $Al_{76}Si_{76}O_{190}(OH)_{152}$ model the INH molecule was orientated along the cylinder section (H1) and in the $Al_{152}Si_{152}O_{380}(OH)_{304}$ model the INH molecule was orientated along the nanotube (H2) (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. Adsorption complexes H1 (a) and H2 (b) of the INH molecule adsorbed on the internal surface of HLNTs optimized with Compass FF, views from (001) and (100) planes. The atoms of silicon, aluminium, hydrogen, carbon, nitrogen and oxygen are described in yellow, pink, white, grey, blue and red, respectively. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

After the optimization, INH had similar behaviour in the adsorption of halloysite surface for both models. A conformational change was produced in the INH molecule where the carbonyl group was oriented in a perpendicular direction with respect to the heterocyclic ring. The carbonyl group and the heterocyclic N atom were approached to be coordinated with the H atoms of the OH group of HLNT surface, whereas the hydrazine moiety was oriented towards the centre of the nanotube. In both adsorption complexes the adsorbate maintained a similar orientation with respect to the HLNT with the heterocyclic ring in a parallel disposition with respect to the mineral surface. In H1 the main adsorbate-surface interactions were strong H bonds between the hydroxyl groups of mineral surface and the carbonyl and heterocyclic N atom of adsorbate with $d(\text{CO}\cdots\text{HO})=1.94\text{\AA}$ and $d(\text{N}\cdots\text{HO})=1.56\text{\AA}$ distances. Additional electrostatic interactions were detected between the N atom of the NH_2 group of INH with the H of OH groups of HLNT surface with $d(\text{HN}\cdots\text{HO}) = 3.05\text{\AA}$. In H2, similar interactions were observed with $d(\text{CO}\cdots\text{HO})=1.69\text{\AA}$, and $d(\text{N}\cdots\text{HO})=1.59\text{\AA}$ distances. Also, the N of the aromatic ring had interactions with the H of the OH group of HLNT surface, the distance is 1.59\AA . Additional electrostatic interactions were detected between the N atom of the NH group of INH with the hydroxyl H atoms of HLNT surface with $d(\text{HN}\cdots\text{HO}) = 2.89\text{\AA}$.

4. Conclusions

Interaction of INH with HLNTs occurs according to two simple processes: adsorption and precipitation of drug molecules onto the nanoclay inner and outer surfaces. Formation of the INH-loaded HLNTs is a spontaneous process, endothermic and endoentropic that increases the thermodynamic stability of the system. Solid state characterization corroborates the effective interaction between the components. The adsorption of INH on the internal surface of HLNTs was possible to be modelled at molecular level with molecular modeling methods finding conformational changes in the molecule and strong hydrogen bond between the carbonyl group and heterocyclic N atom with the hydroxyl H atoms of the mineral surface. Effective loading of INH and the total amount adsorbed by the clay nanotubes as well as the measured activation energies of the interactions are promising features for the design of modified delivery systems able to promote the patient compliance in the treatment of tuberculosis. Complementary studies will be performed to assess biocompatibility and delivery release patterns of the drug from the nanotubes.

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